

THE STUDY OF DERMATOGLYPHICS IN TYPE II DIABETES MELLITUS OF NORTH INDIAN POPULATION

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ABSTRACT

Aims: To analyze the dermatoglyphic pattern quantitatively using palmar angles among varying gender bilaterally in North Indian population and identify its significance. **Methods:** The present study was conducted in the Department of Anatomy, Index Medical College, Indore (M.P.), India. Subjects of the age group 35-65 years was chosen from North Indian Population. Patients and controls were selected randomly from Index Medical College and Hospital, Indore (M.P) India, and other Hospitals or Clinics. Cases were selected as clinically diagnosed patients of Diabetes Mellitus II. The bilateral rolled finger and palm prints of 100 Diabetes Mellitus II patients were compared to 100 controls. **Results:** Shows that the comparison of right atd angle in male between healthy subjects and type II diabetes mellitus patients, which are statistically significant. ($p < 0.001$). whereas right tda, right dat, left atd, left tda, left dat angle is not statistically significant. **Conclusions:** Palmar angles of right dat, left tda, and left dat is increased in healthy male subjects as compared to type II diabetes mellitus. While Right atd, right tda, and left atd is decreased.

KEYWORDS : Dermatoglyphics, T2DM, atd, angle, dat angle, adt angle.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus:

Diabetes is a dangerous and chronic condition that arises when either the pancreas does not make enough insulin or the body does not utilize insulin adequately¹. It is characterised by excessive amounts of hyperglycaemia in the blood, which can cause gradual damage to most tissues and organs of the body, including the heart, blood vessels, eyes, kidneys, skin, and nerves. According to the International Diabetes Federation, there were 425 million diabetics in 2017, with more than 629 million projected by 2045. Diabetes mellitus is divided into two types: type I and type II (formerly known as insulin and non-insulin diabetes mellitus). Type II diabetes is the most common type (affecting around 90% of diabetics). It was previously known as non-insulin-dependent or adult-onset diabetes. Type II diabetes symptoms are often mild or absent. As a result, the condition may go undetected for several years, until problems arise².

Dermatoglyphics:

Dermatoglyphics (Fingerprints) refers to the study of all features of ridged skin³. Cummins and Midlo first formulated this term in 1943, derived from the Greek words "dermato" which means skin and "glyphics" means carvings⁴. The ridged skin (also known as the friction ridges skin) is located on the digit and palmar surface of the hands (known as fingerprints and palm prints) and on the plantar surface and the toe of the feet. It is believed that the mechanical function of these ridges conveys a firmer grip and prevents slippage⁵, and is also believed to enhance the sense of touch⁶.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was conducted in the Department of Anatomy, Index Medical College, Indore (M.P.), India. Subjects of the age group 35-65 years was chosen from North Indian Population. Patients and controls were selected randomly from Index Medical College and Hospital, Indore (M.P) India, and other Hospitals or Clinics. Cases were selected as clinically diagnosed patients of Diabetes Mellitus II. The bilateral rolled finger and palm prints of 100 Diabetes Mellitus II patients were compared to 100 controls.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Subjects included in the study should be between 35- 65 years of age both sexes.

- Cases should be diagnosed with Diabetes Mellitus II.
- The study population should belong to North Indian Population

Exclusion Criteria:

- Individuals suffering from any skin disease like eczema, leprosy etc. will be excluded.
- Subjects with congenital malformation of hand, apparent hand anomalies, inflammation, trauma, deformities and with the surgery of hands will be excluded from the study.
- Patients with deformed finger and palm prints, infection, and injuries of fingers and palms, scars of burns of fingers and palms of both hands.

The palm prints of diabetic patients and controls were taken by Ink Method as described by CUMMINS and MIDLO.

Materials used:

Blue Stamp Pad Ink, Stamp Pad, A4 Size Paper, Magnifying Lens, Soap/Hand wash and towel-wash and dry the hands, Scale, Pencil or Pen and Eraser, Masks and hand Sanitizer, A Protractor - to measure atd, angle and Needle - for ridge counting.

Procedure

1. Participants were instructed to wash and dry their hands with soap and water. The oily layer was carefully removed.
2. A drop of ink was applied to the palm. The whole palmar area was coated with ink. The uniformity of the ink distributed across the palm was confirmed. Cotton puffs were used to fill up the gaps.
3. A spherical bottle was placed on the side of the table. The bottle was covered with the A4 paper sheet.
4. By putting the fingertips of the right hand over the A4 paper sheet, the upper end of the paper was arranged to remain in contact with the bottle.
5. The fingers and palm also were rolled over with minimal pressure, forcing the bottle and paper to move forward. The palmar prints were collected in this manner.
6. Using cotton puffs, the fingers were covered with ink and gently rolled. The prints received were examined for clarity and were reprinted if required.
7. The participants were then instructed to wash their hands.
8. The same method was followed for the left hand as well.
9. The prints have been scanned and stored.

10. A magnifying glass was used to examine the fingerprints. On the same paper, quantitative parameters were examined and recognized.

Quantitative Analysis

The quantitative analyses include angles atd, dat, and adt.

Palmar Angles measurement:

- **atd angle:** The atd angle is the angle between two straight lines joining the radial and ulnar triradii to the hypothenar triradius.
- **dat angle:** This angle was measured by lines drawn from the digital triradius "d" to the digital triradius "a" and from this triradius to the axial triradius "t".
- **tda angle:** This angle was measured by lines drawn from the axial triradius "t" to digital triradius "d" and from this triradius to the digital triradius "a"

Statistical Analysis

The obtained data was statistically analysed using SPSS 21 version. To describe about the data descriptive statistics, the mean & standard deviation was used for continuous variables. To find the prevalence between the Type II Diabetes mellitus and Healthy subjects in male and female thep value was used. The level of significance was setup at p value <0.05.

RESULTS

The palmar dermatoglyphics pattern in type II diabetes mellitus was studied in 200 samples comprising of 50 male diabetic patients, 50 female diabetic patient (right and left hand) and 50 male non diabetic patient, 50 female non diabetic patients (right and left hand).

Table no. 1: Correlate the palmar angles in Type II Diabetes mellitus and Healthy subjects in male and female.

Parameter	Male subjects					Female Subjects				
	Healthy		Type II DM		P value	Healthy		Type II DM		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Right atd	38.22	3.47	41.32	4.04	0.0001	36.56	4.79	43.24	3.63	0.0001
Right tda	77.54	2.05	77.56	2.05	0.9451	77.52	2.04	78.56	3.62	0.0131
Right dat	58.02	1.90	57.88	1.89	0.6020	58	1.88	57.84	1.71	0.5297
Left atd	38.32	2.92	39.3	4.17	0.0557	38.06	5.15	42.64	3.21	0.0001
Left tda	78	1.65	77.94	1.70	0.8003	77.9	1.68	78.1	1.75	0.5645
Left dat	58.78	1.78	58.52	1.62	0.2813	58.74	1.76	58.44	1.69	0.2203

According to table no. 1, Correlate the palmar angles in Type II Diabetes mellitus and Healthy subjects in male and female. Shows that the comparison of right atd angle in male between healthy subjects and type II diabetes mellitus patients, which are statistically significant. (p <0.001). whereas right tda, right dat, left atd, left tda, left dat angle is not statistically significant. Shows that the comparison of right atd, right tda and left atd angle in female between healthy subjects and type II diabetes mellitus patients, which are statistically significant. (p <0.001). whereas right tda, right dat, left tda, and left dat angle is not statistically significant.

DISCUSSION

Comparison of mean value of atd angle of healthy subjects in the present and previous studies: The observations were similar to the previous studies of Jaja et al (2008)⁷, Anibor E et al (2011)⁸ and Sangeeta et al (2019)⁹. The values were higher when compared to the studies of Enna CD et al. (1969)¹⁰, Oladipo GS et al. (2007)¹¹, and Rosa A et al (2009)¹².

Comparison of mean value of atd angle of Type II diabetes mellitus subjects in the present and previous studies: The observations were similar to the previous studies of Sharma MK et al (2012)¹³, Bala A et al (2016)¹⁴, and Sangeeta et al (2019)⁹. The values were higher when compared to the studies of Ojha (2014)¹⁵. The values of the current study were low than the reports of Devi S. et al (2016)¹⁶.

Comparison of mean value of dat angle of Type II diabetes mellitus subjects in the present and previous studies: The observations were similar to the previous studies of Bala A et al (2015)¹⁴, Mittal & lata (2013)¹⁷. The values were higher when compared to the studies of Sharma et al (2012)¹³. The values of the current study were low than the reports of Ojha (2014)¹⁵.

Comparison of mean value of dat angle of Healthy subjects in the present and previous studies: The observations were similar to the previous studies of Bala A et al (2015)¹⁴ and Sharma et al (2012)¹³. The values were higher when compared to the studies of Ojha (2014)¹⁵. The values of the current study were low than the reports of Mittal & lata (2013)¹⁷.

Comparison of mean value of adt angle of Type II diabetes mellitus subjects in the present and previous studies: The observations were similar to the previous studies of Bala A et al (2015)¹⁴, Ojha (2014)¹⁵. The values of the current study were low than the reports of Sharma et al (2012)¹³ and Mittal & lata (2013)¹⁴.

Comparison of mean value of adt angle of Healthy subjects in the present and previous studies: The values were higher when compared to the studies of Bala et al (2015)¹⁴. The values of the current study were lower than the reports of Ojha (2014)¹⁵, Mittal & lata et al (2013)¹⁷, and Sharma et al (2012)¹³.

CONCLUSION

Palmar angles of right dat, left tda, and left dat is increased in healthy male subjects as compared to type II diabetes mellitus. While Right atd, right tda, and left atd is decreased. Palmar angles of right dat and left dat is increased in healthy female subjects as compared to type II diabetes mellitus. Whereas Right atd, right tda, left atd and left tda is decreased. This study results may be helpful in early diagnosis of type II diabetes.

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